

Present status of epigenetic drugs in cancer treatment

Table 3: Clinical trials of AZA

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier (NCT)
AZA with or without Vorinostat or Lenalidomide	MDS, Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML)	III, II	Closed	NCT01522976
AZ + Gemtuzumab Ozogamicin	AML(previously untreated)	II	Closed	NCT00658814
AZ + Midostaurin	AML(Elderly patients)	II, I	Active	NCT01093573
Low dose AZ + Lenalidomide + low dose dexamethasone	Multiple myeloma (relapsed or refractory)II, I	II, I	Active	NCT01155583
AZ + argramostim	Maintenance therapy for poor risk AML and MDS	II	Active	NCT01700673
AZA or DAC	MDS (before stem cell transplant)	II	Active	NCT01812252
AZ + bortezomib	Refractory or relapsed AML or MDS	I	Active	NCT00624936
AZ + Cytarabin + Mitoxantrone Hydrochloride	High risk AML	I	Active	NCT 01839240
AZ + Entinostat	Stage IA to IIIA non-small cell cancer	No phase specified	Active	NCT01885673
AZ + Lenalidomide	Advanced MDS	II,I	Completed	NCT00352001
AZ + Entinostat	Advanced non-small cell Lung cancer	II,I	Closed	NCT00387465
Vorinosta + AZA	MDS or AML	II,I	Closed	NCT00392353
AZ + Gemtuzumab ozogamici + orinostat	Relapsed or refractory AML	II,I	Completed	NCT00895934
AZ + Etanercept	MDS	II,I	Completed	NCT00118287
AZ + Amifostine	MDS	II	Completed	NCT00005598
AZ + Phenylbutyrate	AML, MDS, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma(NHL), multiple myeloma, non-small cell cancer, prostate cancer	II	Completed	NCT00006019
AZ +/- Entinostat	MDS, CML, AML	II	Closed	NCT00313586
AZA	CML after allogenic Bone Marrow transplantation (BMT)	II	Completed	NCT00813124
AZA	Relapsed MDS, Chronic CML or AML(who have undergone stem cell transplantation)	II	Completed	NCT01083706
AZ + Entinostat	Metastatic colorectal cancer	II	Completed	NCT01105377
AZ + SCT after chemotherapy	Acute AML(older patient)	II	Closed	NCT01168219
AZA	Non-small cell Lung cancer(previously treated)	II	Closed	NCT01281124
AZ + Entinostat	Advanced Breast cancer	II	Closed	NCT01349959
AZA	Persistent or metastatic follicular or papillary thyroid cancer	I	Completed	NCT00004062
AZ + Phenylbutyrate	AML, MDS	I	Completed	NCT00004871

AZ + Phenylbutyrate	Advanced or metastatic Solid tumors that have not responded to previous treatment	I	Completed	NCT00005639
AZ + MS275	MDS, CML or AML	I	closed	NCT00101179
AZ + Interferon α -2b	Stage III or IV melanoma or stage IV kidney cancer	I	Completed	NCT00217542
AZ + Vorinostat	Locally recurrent and metastatic Nasopharyngeal cancer and nasal natural killer T cell lymphoma	I	Closed	NCT00336033
AZ + Belinostat	Advanced hematologic cancer	I	Closed	NCT00351975
AZ + Interferon α	Metastatic melanoma	I	Closed	NCT00398450
AZ + Oxaliplatin	Advanced cancer relapsed or refractory to any platinum therapy	I	closed	NCT01039155
AZ + Mitoxantron + Etoposide phosphat + Cytarabine	Relapsed or refractory AML	I	Closed	NCT01249430
AZ + Metoxantrone + toposide	Poor prognosis AML	I	Closed	NCT01260714
AZA	AML, MDS(After chemotherapy and donor lymphocyte infusion)	I	Closed	NCT01390311
AZ + Sonidegib	Myeloid malignancies	I	Closed	NCT02129101

Table 4: Clinical trials of DAC

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier (NCT)
Clofarabine or Daunorubicin and Cytarabine followed by DAC	AML(newly diagnosed, in elderly patient)	III	Active	NCT01041703
DAC followed by Mitoxantrone, Etoposide, Cytarabine	Relapsed or refractory AML or high risk MDS	II,I	Active	NCT01729845
DA + Ruxolitinib	Accelerated phase MPN(myeloproliferative neoplasm) or post MPN AML	II, I	Active	NCT02076191
DA + Cytarabine + auronubicin	AML	II	Active	NCT 01627041
DAC + total body irradiation followed by BMT and Cyclophosphamide	Relapsed or refractory AML	II	Active	NCT01707004
DA + Midostaurin	AML (newly diagnosed)	II	Active	NCT 01846624
DA + Omacetazine Mepesuccinat + Cytarabine	AML(newly diagnosed)	II	Active	NCT02029414
DA + DEC205/NY-ESO1 fusion protein CDX 1401	MDS, AML	I	Active	NCT01834248
DA + Bortezomi + Sorafenib tosylate	AML	I	Active	NCT01861314

DA + Cytarabine	Newly diagnosed AML, High risk MDS or Myeloproliferative neoplasm	Not specified	Active	NCT02121418
DA + peripheral stem cell transplantation	Relapsed Leukemia, MDS, CML	II,I	Completed	NCT00002832
DA + Tretinoin	MDS	II,I	Closed	NCT00382200
DAC	MDS	II	Completed	NCT00003361
DA + Imatinib mesylate	CML	II	Completed	NCT00054431
DAC	Metastatic papillary or follicular thyroid cancer	II	Completed	NCT00085293
DAC	Myelofibrosis	II	Closed	NCT00095784
DAC	Maintenance therapy for previously untreated AML	II	Closed	NCT00416598
DAC	AML (previously untreated)	II	Closed	NCT00492401
DA +/- Bortezomib	AML(elderly)	II	Closed	NCT01420926
DAC or Cytarabine + Tosedostat	AML(newly diagnosed) or High risk MDS	II	Completed	NCT01567059
DAC followed by Idarubicin + cytarabine	Relapsed or refractory AML or MDS	II	Completed	NCT01607645
DAC	Melanoma or advanced cancer	II	Completed	NCT00002980
DAC	Unresectable lung or esophageal cancer or malignant mesothelioma	I	Completed	NCT00019825
DAC	Advanced solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00030615
DAC or Dapsone +/- Celecoxib	Pulmonary and pleural malignancies	I	Completed	NCT00037817
DA + Doxorubicin + cyclophosphamide	Relapsed or refractory solid tumors or neuroblastoma in children	I	Completed	NCT00075634
DA + Valproic acid	Non-small cell lung cancer	I	Completed	NCT00109824
DA +/-Valproic acid	Relapsed or refractory non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL)	I	Completed	NCT00109824
DA + FR901228 (Romidepsin)	Relapsed or refractory Leukemia, MDS and MPD	I	Completed	NCT00114257
DA + Vorinostat	Advanced solid tumors or relapsed non-Hodgkin's lymphoma , AML,ALL, CML	I	Completed	NCT00275080
DA + Vorinostat	Relapsed, refractory or poor prognosis hematologic cancer	I	Completed	NCT00357708
DA + Bortezomib	AML	I	Completed	NCT00703300
DA + Vorinosta + cytarabine	Relapsed or refractory AML	I	Closed	NCT01130506

Table 5: Clinical trials of SGI-110

Drug	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier (NCT)
SGI-110 + Carboplatin	Ovarian cancer	II, I	Active, not recruiting	NCT01696032

SGI-110 + GVA + Cyclophosphamide	Metastatic colon cancer	I	Not yet recruiting	NCT01966289
SGI-110 + Irinotecan	Metastatic colon cancer	II, I	active	NCT01896856
SGI-110	Advanced hepatocellular carcinoma	II	Active	NCT01752933
SGI-110	MDS	II, I	Active, not recruiting	NCT01261312
SGI-110	Acute AML (elderly)	II	active	NCT02096055
SGI-110	Higher risk MDS	II	Active	NCT02131597
SGI-110	AML	I	Active	NCT02293993
SGI-110	IPSS high and intermediate 2 MDS, AML with 20-30% blast or CML type 2 not responding to AZA or DAC after at least 6 courses or relapsing after response	II	Active	NCT02197676

Table 6: Clinical trials of EGCG (Green tea catechin extract/ polyphenon E)

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier (NCT)
Green tea catechin extract	ER PR negative stage I, II, IIIA and IIIB Breast cancer	I	Completed	NCT00516243
Green tea catechin	Adenocarcinoma of prostate, Stage I, II prostate cancer	I	Completed	NCT00459407
Polyphenon E	High grade prostatic intraepithelial neoplasia	II	Active(not recruiting)	NCT00596011
Green tea catechin extract	Prostate cancer (stage I, IIA, IIB undergoing surgery)	II	Terminated	NCT01340599
Green tea catechin extract	Non-metastatic bladder cancer	II	Terminated	NCT00666562
Polyphenon E	High risk colorectal cancer	II	Active, not recruiting	NCT01606124
Green tea catechin extract	Multiple myeloma and plasma cell neoplasm	II	Active, not recruiting	NCT00942422
Green tea catechin extract	Cervical cancer with Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) and low grade Cervical intraepithelial Neoplasia (CIN)	II	Completed	NCT00303823
Green tea catechin extract	Lung cancer, tobacco use disorder	II	Completed	NCT00573885
Green tea catechin extract	Breast cancer	II	Completed	NCT00917735
Green tea catechin extract	Bronchial dysplasia(precancerous condition)	II	Terminated	NCT00611650
Green tea catechin extract	Barrett esophagus	I	Completed	NCT00233935

Table 7: Clinical trials of Vorinostat

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier (NCT)
Vorinostat, Temozolomide or Bevacizumab + Radiotherapy	High grade glioma (newly diagnosed)	III, II	Closed	NCT01236560
Vorinostat	Progressive or Relapsed advanced malignant pleural mesothelioma	III	Closed	NCT00265577
Vorinosta + paclitaxe + Bevacizumab	Metastatic breast cancer	II, I	Closed	NCT00368875
Vorinosta + chemotherapy	Relapsed or refractory lymphoma or previously untreated T-cell NHL or Mantle cell lymphoma (MCL)	II,I	Completed	NCT00601718
Vorinosta + Temozolomid + Radiation therapy	Glioblastoma multiforme	II, I	Closed	NCT00731731
Vorinosta + Cladribine and Rituximab	MCL, CLL or relapsed B-cell NHL	II,I	Closed	NCT00764517
Vorinosta + Chemotherapy	CLL or small lymphocytic leukemia(previously untreated)	II,I	Closed	NCT00918723
Vorinosta + chemotherapy	Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma	II,I	Closed	NCT00972478
Vorinostat	Relapsed or refractory advanced Hodgkin's lymphoma (HL)	II	Completed	NCT001320328
Vorinostat	Metastatic and/or locally advanced or locally recurrent thyroid cancer	II	Completed	NCT00134043
Vorinostat	Low grade NHL	II	closed	NCT00253630
Vorinostat	Kidney cancer	II	Closed	NCT00481078
Vorinosta + chemotherapy	Advanced od metastatic non-small cell lung cancer	II	Completed	NCT00481078
Carboplatin and Nab-paclitaxel with or without Vorinostat	Breast cancer(newly diagnosed operable)	II	Completed	NCT00616967
Vorinostat	Progressive metastatic Prostate cancer	II	Completed	NCT00330161
Vorinostat	Progressive stage IV Breast cancer	II	Completed	NCT00132002
Vorinosta + Capicitabine	Head and neck cancer(recurrent and metastatic)	II	Closed	NCT01267240
Vorinostat	Non-small cell lung cancer(stage IIIb, IV or recurrent)	II	Completed	NCT00138203
Carboplatin and paclitaxel with or without Vorinostat	Non-small cell lung cancer	II	Closed	NCT01413750
Vorinostat	Refractory malignancies	I	Completed	NCT00005634
Vorinosta + Capicitabine	Metastatic or unresectable solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00138177

Vorinostat + chemotherapy	Metastatic and unresectable colorectal cancer and other solid malignancies	I	Completed	NCT00138177
Vorinostat with or without Isotretinoin	Recurrent or refractory solid tumors, Lymphoma and leukemia	I	Completed	NCT00217412
Vorinosta + Bortezomib	Metastatic and unresectable solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00227513
Vorinosta + Gemcitabine	Metastatic and unresectable solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00243100
Vorinosta + Temozolamide	Malignant gliomas	I	Closed	NCT00268385
Vorinosta + Paclitaxe + Carboplatin	Advanced or refractory solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00287937
Vorinosta + Doxorubicin	Advanced solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00331955
Vorinosta + Cytarabine + Etoposide	Acute leukemia or MDS or myeloproliferative disease (MPD)	I	Completed	NCT00357305
Vorinosta + Bortezomib + Doxorubicin	Relapsed or refractory multiple myeloma	I	Closed	NCT00744354
Vorinosta + Capicitabine + radiation	Non metastatic pancreatic cancer	I	Closed	NCT00983268
Vorinosta + Flavopiridol	Relapsed or refractory acute leukemia or CML or refractory anemia	I	Completed	NCT00278330
Vorinosta + emozolamide	Relapsed or refractory primary brain tumors or spinal cord tumors	I	Completed	NCT01076530
Vorinosta + Isotretinoin	High risk refractory or recurrent Neuroblastoma	I	Closed	NCT01208454
Vorinosta + Isotretinoin and chemotherapy	Embryonal tumors (in younger patients)	Not specified	Closed	NCT00867178
Vorinosta + Temozolomide	Recurrent or progressive glioblastoma	Not specified	Completed	NCT00867178
Vorinosta + Carboplatin or Paclitaxel	Advanced solid tumors	Not specified	Closed	NCT01281176
Cytarabin and Daunorubicin or Idarubicin and cytarabine with or without Vorinostat	AML(young Previously untreated)	III	Active	NCT01802333
Vorinosta + combination chemotherapy	HIV related diffuse large B-cell NHL + other aggressive B-cell Lymphoma	II, I	Active	NCT01193842
Vorinosta + Bortezomib	NHL as maintenance therapy after autologous stem cell transplant (SCT)	II	Active	NCT00992446
Vorinostat	Metastatic melanoma of eye	II	Active	NCT01587352
Temsirolimu + Vorinostat	Metastatic prostate cancer	I	Active	NCT01174199
Vorinosta + Paclitaxel and Carboplatin	Metastatic and recurrent solid tumors and HIV infection	I	Active	NCT01249443

Vorinosta + Alisertib	Relapsed or recurrent HL, B-cell NHL or Peripheral T-cell Lymphoma	I	Active	NCT01567709
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Table 8: Clinical trials of Romidepsin

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Romidepsin	Recurrent High grade glioma	II,I	Completed	NCT00085540
Romidepsin	Refractory progressive small cell cancer or non-small cell cancer	II	Completed	NCT00020202
Romidepsin	CTCL, PTCL	II	Closed	NCT00020436, NCT00007345
Romidepsin	MDS, AML, Intermediate grade or follicular NHL	II	Completed	NCT00042822
Romidepsin	Refractory AML	II	completed	NCT00062075
Romidepsin	Relapsed or refractory multiple myeloma	II	Completed	NCT00066638
Romidepsin	Relapsed or refractory NHL	II	Completed	NCT44477194
Romidepsin	Previously treated, unresectable, locally advanced or metastatic colorectal cancer	II	Completed	NCT00077337
Romidepsin	Squamous cell carcinoma of head and neck (unresectable, recurrent or metastatic)	II	Completed	NCT00084682
Romidepsin	Relapsed small cell lung cancer	II	Completed	NCT00086827
Romidepsin	Thyroid cancer (recurrent and metastatic, unresponsive to radioactive iodine)	II	Completed	NCT00098813
Romidepsin	Metastatic Breast cancer	II	Completed	NCT00098397
Romidepsin	Malignant melanoma(unresectable stage III, stage IV)	II	Closed	NCT00104884
Romidepsin	Soft tissue sarcoma(metastatic and unresectable)	II	Closed	NCT00112463
Romidepsin	Solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00019318
Romidepsin	CLL, Small Lymphocytic Lymphoma, AML, ALL	I	Completed	NCT00024180
Romidepsin	Refractory or recurrent solid tumors or Leukemia	I	Completed	NCT00053963
Romidepsin_ Bortezomib	CLL, chronic lymphocytic Lymphoma, indolent B-cell Lymphoma, PTCL or CTCL	I	Closed	NCT00963274
Romidepsin	Thyroid or other advanced cancer	I	Completed	NCT00048334
Romidepsi + Rituxima + Lenalidomide	Recurrent or refractory B-cell NHL	II, I	Approved, not yet active	NCT02281279

Romidepsi + Lenalidomide	PTCL (previously untreated)	II	Approved, not yet active	NCT02232516
Romidepsin	Lymphoma, CLL or solid tumor with liver dysfunction	I	Active	NCT01638533
Romidepsi + Alisertib	Relapsed or refractory B-cell or T-cell Lymphoma	I	Active	NCT01897012

Table 9: Clinical trials of Panabinostat

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Panobinostat + Everolimus	Recurrent Multiple myeloma, NHL or HL	II, I	Active	NCT00918333
Panobinosta + Everolimus	Metastatic and unresectable Renal cell cancer unresponding to treatment with Sunitinib malate or Sorafenib tosylate	II, I	Active	NCT01582009
Panobinostat	Relapsed or refractory NHL	II	Active	NCT01261247
Panobinosta + Letrozole	Metastatic Breast cancer	II, I	Temporarily closed	NCT01105312
Panobinosta + Imatinib mesylate	CML(previously treated)	I	Completed	NCT00686218
Panobinosta + pirubicin	Metastatic malignant solid tumor	I	Closed	NCT00878904
Panobinosta + Everolimus	Relapsed or refractory lymphoma or multiple myeloma	I	Completed	NCT00962504

Table 10: Clinical trials of Belinostat

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Belinostat + Yttrium Y 90 Ibritumomab Tiuxetan	Relapsed aggressive B-cell NHL	II	Active	NCT01686165
Belinosta + cisplatin + Etoposide	Small cell lung cancer and other advanced cancer	I	Active	NCT00926640
Belinostat	Solid tumors and Lymphoma with varying degrees of hepatic dysfunction.	I	Active	NCT01273155
Belinostat	Liver cancer (unresectable)	II, I	Completed	NCT00321594
Belinosta + cisplati + Doxorubici + Cyclophosphamide	Advanced or recurrent thymic malignancies (as a first line treatment)	II, I	Closed	NCT01100944

Belinostat	Ovarian epithelial cancer, Primary peritoneal cancer or Fallopian tube cancer or ovarian low malignant potential tumor	II	Closed	NCT00301756
Belinostat	Relapsed or refractory Aggressive B-cell NHL	II	Completed	NCT00303953
Belinostat	AML	II	Completed	NCT00357032
Belinostat	Unresectable Malignant melanoma of chest (as a second line therapy)	II	Completed	NCT00365053
Belinostat	MDS	II	Completed	NCT00357162
Belinostat	Advanced thymic tumor	II	Completed	NCT00589290
Belinosta + Carboplatin	Persistent ovarian epithelial cancer, Fallopian tube cancer or primary peritoneal cancer unresponsive to carboplatin and cisplatin	II	Completed	NCT00993616
Belinosta + Bortezomib	Advanced solid tumors and lymphomas	I	Completed	NCT00348985
Belinosta + Isotretinoin	Unresectable metastatic solid tumors	I	Closed	NCT00334789
Belinosta + Bortezomib	Relapsed or refractory acute leukemia or MDS	I	Closed	NCT01075425

Table 11: Clinical trials of Quisinostat, CHR-2845 (Tefinostat) and CHR-3996

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Quisinostat	Advanced or refractory leukemia or MDS	I	Terminated	NCT00676728
Quisinosta + Bortezomi + Dexamethasone	Multiple myeloma	I	Completed	NCT01464112
Quisinostat	CTCL (previously treated)	II	Active, not recruiting	NCT01486277
Quisinostat	Advanced solid malignancies and lymphoma	I	Completed	NCT00677105
Tefinostat	Hematological disease or lymphoid malignancies	I	Completed	NCT00820508
CHR-3996	Advanced solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00697879

Table 12: Clinical trials of MS275 (Entinostat)

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Entinosta + GM-CSF	MDS and/or relapsed or refractory AML or ALL	II	Completed	NCT00462605
Entinostat	Hematologic cancers	II	Closed	NCT00015925
Entinosta + Isotretinoin	Metastatic and advanced solid tumors or lymphoma	I	Completed	NCT00098891

Entinosta + clofarabine	Newly diagnosed, relapsed or refractory poor-risk ALL or Bilineage or Biphenotypic leukemia	I	Completed	NCT01132573
Entinostat	Advanced solid tumors or lymphoma	I	Completed	NCT00020579
Exemestane +/-Entinostat	Postmenopausal recurrent hormone receptor positive advanced Breast cancer	III	Active	NCT02115282
Entinosta + Aldesleukin	Metastatic Kidney cancer	II, I	Active	NCT01038778
Entinosta + Lapatinib ditosylate and Trastuzumab	Locally recurrent or distant relapsed Metastatic Breast cancer Previously treated with Trastuzumab only	I	Active	NCT01434303

Table 13: Clinical trials CI994 (Tacedinaline)

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Tacedinaline	Advanced Myeloma	II	Completed	NCT00005624
Gemcitabine +/-Tacedinaline	Advanced non-small cell Lung cancer	III	Completed	NCT00005093
Gemcitabine +/-Tacedinaline	Advanced Pancreatic Cancer	II	Completed	NCT00004861

Table 14: Clinical trials of Sodium phenyl butyrate

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Sodium Phenylbutyrate	Progressive and recurrent CNS malignancy(high grade glioma, medulloblastoma) in child	II	Closed	NCT00006238
Sodium Phenylbutyrate + Fluorouracil	Advanced colorectal cancer	II, I	Terminated	NCT0002796
Phenylbutyrate + Tretenoin	Hematologic cancer	I	Completed	NCT00006239
Sodium Phenylbutyrate	Refractory solid tumor and lymphoma in children	I	Completed	NCT00002909
Sodium Phenylbutyrate + dexamethasone + Sargramostim	Refractory or relapsed AML	II	Completed	NCT0006240

Table 15: Clinical trials of Valproic acid

Drugs	Condition	Phases	Status	Clinicaltrial.gov identifier(NCT)
Valproic acid + Temozolomid + radiation therapy	Brain tumor	II	Closed	NCT00302159

Valproic aci + DAC	Refractory or relapsed AML or previously treated CLL or small Lymphocytic Lymphoma	I	Completed	NCT00079378
Valproic acid	Recurrent and refractory solid tumors or CNS tumors	I	Completed	NCT00107458
Valproic aci + Epirubicin	Solid tumors	I	Completed	NCT00246103
Valproic acid	Kaposi's sarcoma	Not specified	Completed	NCT00075777
Valproic acid	Progressive non-metastatic prostate cancer	II	Active	NCT00670046
Valproic acid	Advanced follicular thyroid cancer	II	Active	NCT01182285